

PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF WASTE REDUCTION IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES.

A.Najmiddinov¹

U.Akhmedov²

M.Urozov³

¹⁻²⁻³Termiz Institute of Engineering Technology
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7466199>

Abstract: It is necessary to improve technological processes in industrial enterprises. Then it will be possible to produce waste-free or low-waste products. Such a process is a closed process, in which there is no waste at all or a different product is produced from the waste.

Keywords: chemical industry, enterprises, chemicals, acids, alkalis, salts, mineral fertilizers, polymers, synthetic fibers and other types of products.

Introduction. It is known that various chemical substances, namely acids, alkalis, salts, mineral fertilizers, polymers, synthetic fibers and other types of products are produced in chemical industry enterprises. The chemical industry is divided into several branches depending on the products it produces, the raw materials it uses, as well as its technological processes. A peculiarity of the chemical industry is that the enterprises belonging to this field operate in an integral relationship with each other. The raw materials used by them are also often used by these enterprises. In this case, the integrated use of raw materials, that is, the intermediate product created as a result of the activity of one enterprise, can be used by another enterprise. With the development of the chemical industry, the production of consumer goods also increased significantly. This in itself led to the improvement of the population's well-being, but there is another aspect of the issue that worries everyone.

The development of the chemical industry, the widespread use of chemicals, industrial waste, and the increase in chemical production waste have led to a high level of poisoning of the natural environment. However, it is impossible to imagine solving the problem of human needs of the development of society without chemistry, and it is also impossible to abandon the use of chemical compounds in economic activities. Therefore, it is necessary to focus all our attention on the standard of their production, the rules of procedure and our rational use of them, taking into account environmental and social factors.

The widespread use of toxic chemicals poses many problems to the science of hygiene. Toxic chemicals are poisons by name. The effect of these substances is dangerous only for animals, insects or plants. Pollution of the external environment with toxic chemicals, in turn, has a negative effect on the health of the population and all animals, therefore, it is necessary to prevent the harmful consequences of the large use of toxic chemicals in the public economy, as well as , devising ways to protect atmospheric air, water and soil from enterprise waste and wastewater is one of the urgent problems.

Issues related to the sanitary-hygienic evaluation of toxic chemicals are managed by the Ministry of Health of the Republic.

According to the request of the Ministry of Health, it is not allowed to use imported chemicals without studying the toxicological effects of chemical substances, without thoroughly checking them from all sides. For each chemical substance used in life and agriculture, it is

required to have a special document, methodological instructions, instructions for their use, norms, information on first aid used in case of emergency poisoning.

In the process of using toxic chemicals in agriculture, they are developed based on the hygienic requirements for these substances, taking into account the protection of public health.

The purpose and objectives of the research. In the process of using toxic chemicals, prevention of their residual effects on the human body in objects of the external environment is an urgent problem. In this regard, sanitary control works carried out by sanitary institutions are aimed at protecting people from the effects of toxic chemical residues.

When toxic chemicals are used, determining the amount of their residues in the air in the working area, in the atmospheric air of residential areas, in water and water bodies, in the soil, and to determine whether this amount is more or less with the norms developed on the basis of hygiene by way of comparison, the science of hygiene defines the permissible amount for all toxic chemicals used in life.

The possibility that toxic chemicals can negatively affect human offspring is one of the most complex problems in genetics. The fact that genetic diseases are increasing in the future does not cause concern. The problem of the effect of the used chemicals on the body as an allergen remains one of the most difficult problems to solve. Chemical substances have a negative effect on embryonic cells even when they enter the body in very small quantities. Taking this into account, hygiene workers have developed the permissible standard amount of harmful substances. One of the complex issues in the science of hygiene is the implementation of the developed permissible normative amounts, the organization and implementation of strict state control of the use of toxic chemicals. Taking this into account, in our independent Republic, the rules for working with toxic chemicals, the norms of their use, and the normative amounts have been developed.

For this, it is necessary to improve technological processes in industrial enterprises. Then it will be possible to produce a product without waste or with low waste. Such a process is a closed process, in which there is no waste at all or a different product is produced from the waste. The use of scientific and technical achievements in waste-free production is of great importance in keeping the air of residential areas clean.

Theoretical and practical significance of research results. A special decision was made by the United Nations on the establishment of low-waste and zero-waste industrial enterprises. Another important issue is the replacement of toxic substances with less toxic ones.

For example, if boilers heated by burning coal or fuel oil are heated with gas, harmful substances released into the atmosphere are reduced by 70-90%. The elimination of harmful substances in raw materials is also technologically important. Technological processes should not stop even for a minute. If the process is stopped, waste can accumulate and allow atmospheric air pollution.

Rivers, canals, reservoirs and even underground water in our region are affected by human activities. "Water in irrigated areas is a priceless gift of nature. All life is connected with water. Where water ends, life ends. However, water resources in Central Asia are very limited. Amudarya, which brings 78 cubic kilometers of water per year, and Syrdarya, which brings 36 cubic kilometers, are the main sources of water.

The depletion of water resources and the worsening of the quality of water in the basins are caused by the large-scale development of new lands in our region since the 1960s, the development of industrial and livestock complexes, and collector ditch systems.

Most of the glaciers in Central Asia are located outside Uzbekistan. There is a large reserve of high-quality natural water in the glaciers that supply the rivers in Uzbekistan. Depending on the type of water source and the height of the catchment basin, the period of filling of rivers lasts 1-2 months in spring or summer in smaller rivers and 3-4 months in large rivers. During this period, 70-95% of the annual volume of water flows in the rivers. Some years the rivers are filled with rainwater.

Water is polluted by industrial and communal waste water, oil, radioactive substances, etc. The clean water used in the industry of developed countries is several times more than the water used in communal households. Waste water is considered unsuitable for human drinking water supply. Because water saturated with toxic substances has a negative effect on human health. It causes various infectious diseases. Later, doctors discovered that the germs of poliomyelitis, yellow fever and tuberculosis spread through water.

Conclusion. In the chemical industry, synthetically produced paint, explosives and various medicines, rubber, artificial fiber, etc., require a large amount of clean water. As a result, harmful substances that are not found in nature can be found in the dirty water from such production sources.

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